

Family businesses gaining access to formalization in Amazonas, Peru

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ABSTRACT: In the context of the Amazonas region, Peru, this study focuses on analyzing family businesses in the commerce sector that have embarked on the formalization process during the years 2021 and 2022, specifically in the "Asentamiento Humano 16 de octubre" located in Chachapoyas, Amazonas. This research delves into the business dynamics of this region, aiming to deeply understand how business formalization influences the organizational behavior of these family enterprises. Family businesses play a crucial role in the economy of any country, and their formalization is a relevant process for both local development and the well-being of the involved families. In this study, we explore the positive effects of formalization on these organizations, as well as its impact on the economic and social environment of the communities in which they operate. The choice of "Asentamiento Humano 16 de octubre" in Chachapoyas as the study area is based on the relevance of this region as a representative microcosm of the economic and social dynamics of Amazonas. In this context, we examine how formalization affects the structure, management, and business strategies of family enterprises, and how these, in turn, influence the local economy. Throughout this study, we present a detailed analysis of the data collected from 26 family business owners in the commerce sector within "Asentamiento Humano 16 de octubre." Our research methodology combines qualitative and quantitative approaches to provide a comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing

formalization and its relationship with organizational behavior. The results of this study will provide valuable information for family business owners in the process of formalization, as well as for policymakers interested in promoting sustainable economic growth in the Amazonas region.

Keywords: Family businesses, Organizational behavior, Formalization.

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1. Introduction

INEI (2020), refers that, in the last 27 years (1993 and 2019), Peru's economy has achieved an average annual growth of 4.8%; in the last ten years (2010-2019), the year-on-year economic growth rate was 4.5%. It grew at an average annual rate of 3.2%. The Peruvian economy has maintained growth for 21 consecutive years. The national economy has shown resilience to the ups and downs of the international economy, mainly due to the constant and stable monetary and fiscal policies that have been maintained over the last two decades, as well as the growth of exports in conjunction with its integration policy, and commercialization in various markets around the world.

Family businesses are currently creating jobs and self-employment on a global scale as individualized economic agents; it is also worth mentioning that in developed countries they are part of large companies (to which they provide products and/or services), work clearly and generate profits; however, in developing countries, these family businesses are created to survive, and large companies are not considered as entities that provide opportunities for development and growth, because large companies do (Ansón and Cabeza, 2011).

The European Union supports its family businesses to obtain financing (mainly for their working capital) through financial programs supported by structural funds (European Regional Development Fund [ERDF] and European Social Fund [ESF]); similarly, for these businesses. To gain a foothold in the market and be seen as part of large companies (they are forced to consider them instead of trying to disappear from the market), promote mutual support between companies of different sizes and produce different perceptions of business competitiveness (Watkins and Rodriguez, 2022).

In Latin America, there is a lack of formalization and institutionalization of family businesses (representing temporary alternatives to unemployment and poverty), which is more prevalent in microenterprises, reflected mainly in tax evasion, promotion of business informalization and mobile businesses; similarly, in the financial system, there are more credit restrictions, which is why financial institutions grant loans to most microentrepreneurs who are natural persons (without businesses) because they know that the money they lend is used for commercial purposes (Ramos, 2019).

An example from Latin America in Ecuador, in the First Report on the Study of Family Business in Ecuador' points out that 90.5% (45,250) of the companies registered in the database of the Superintendence of Companies are classified as family businesses, which occupy an important position in its current economy and contribute to its growth and generation of employment; likewise, in the financial sector it participates in the support by granting credit from the public or private sector. However, these family businesses have difficulties in obtaining alternative sources of financing, which are subject to a series of

restrictions to the banking entity (in order to obtain the necessary information from the company and analyze the risks when granting loans. (Rodríguez and Marín, 2017); (Graves and Thomas, 2008).

In Peru, family businesses aims to solve key problems and form part of 90% of existing businesses in the country, they are about 660,000 family businesses, which have manufactured customized products, paid and used as auxiliary fabrics for large companies; however, they present serious institutional, economic and financial problems; Financial entities (banks and non-banks), have access and limited use of financial services (savings and investment financing), although most of these microenterprises need to finance their working capital, hindering their production and expansion in the market (Peñaranda, 2019).

Similarly in North Lima, family businesses cannot obtain financing because it is difficult for them to obtain financing from a third party, even when they require them to invest in resources (working

capital) for the purchase of commodities and/or raw materials; it is worth mentioning that the financing difficulties are the high interest rate, the lack of trust and support for banking entities (i.e. non-bank entities such as municipalities, rural areas, cooperatives, among others. which provide more and better financing facilities). The amount of documents required as a prerequisite, the lack of training in business management and poor knowledge of financing techniques that affect their competitiveness (Castro, 2019); (Sanchez, 2017).

In Chachapoyas, when the socioeconomic diagnosis was made, it was determined that the main economic activities in the area correspond to the primary sector were the different forms of agriculture, livestock and tourism, in the 21 districts, agricultural activities in the province are oriented towards crop diversity (INEI, 2012).

Peruvian family businesses, mostly organized, in the period 2021-2022, are a space with legitimizing potential to carry out this analysis, since different types of companies prevail assuming classification criteria, organizational behavior and formalization of companies in the business sector (Diéguez and López, 2018). The results account that, from the specifications of family businesses, it deals with the non-formalized ones pay lower amounts of dividends, if compared to the counterpart of the formalized ones.

This study made contributions to theoretical and empirical knowledge, on the one hand, it addressed the formalization necessary for this type of companies (De Massis et al., 2013); (Yeung, B. (2003); (Graves and Thomas, 2008.)). On the other hand, it contributed to the literature related to family businesses, as it is linked to the heterogeneity established on profitability, productivity and obtaining financial resources (Cerrato and Piva, 2012). These results have practical implications for the key subjects of management, the direct managers of the companies and the investors, since their organizational behavior will bring them closer to processes of formalization of the company before the bodies created in a given territory, in this modality in Peru to develop it.

In order to conduct this research, the following question was formulated: What is the percentage of family businesses in the commerce sector that have access to business formalization in the Asentamiento Humano 16 de octubre, Chachapoyas, Amazonas, Peru, during 2022?

2. Literature Review and Research Hypothesis

Typologies of family businesses: A look from the heterogeneity of criteria.

The family business assuming a diversity of criteria can be defined as an organization where the family owns most of the properties, particularly the family members intervene and participate in the management of the business, most of the time they tend to transfer the business to the next generation highlighting heterogeneous differentiating characteristics that they share (Chua et al., 2012). Family businesses are organizations

where culture, values and collective interests shape a company derived from business intervention processes (Gallo, 2004)

Research on the formalization of family businesses has shown mixed results (Pukall & Calabrò, 2014), due to the need to establish heterogeneous criteria, in this sense it is necessary to continue investigating the sustained impact of family variants in the formalization processes of these organizations (Alayo et al., 2021). In the exhaustive review of the academic literature, family businesses formalize later and with slow processes (Fernández & Nieto, 2005; Moreno-Menéndez et al., 2021).

Finally, the intervention in the processes of creation of these family businesses are factors that influence the creation of classification processes to establish typologies of family businesses (Alayo et al., 2021; Debellis et al., 2021). In this sense, this research analyzed how the influence of various criteria affect the formalization of the companies.

Hypothesis 1. Family businesses have different criteria for their typologies compared to non-family businesses.

Organizational behavior based on the awareness of business formalization

While family businesses their internal bonding dynamics highlight work, process and results environments, which go through different stages depending on the subjects managing the business (Cruz & Nordqvist, 2012), behavior in strategic decisions is linked to attitude and (Fang et al., 2018). An essential element, in this context is that the involvement of the family generation in the business maintains long-term orientation (Kellermanns et al., 2008).

Widespread research, which has been developed with strict vigilance from the method developed, indicates that companies managed by educated generations with academic degrees tend to formalize their technical operations. For Fernández and Nieto (2005), formalization processes are linked to the sector, showing that family contribution and work relationships can be an opportunity to introduce changes in a company for formalization (Ferraro and Stumpo, 2010).

Hypothesis 2. Having a more advanced formalization affects the company's dividends.

Figure 1. Dynamics: Family businesses and Formalization

3. Methodology

The research design is non-experimental-transectional-descriptive, basically a review of bibliography related to family businesses is performed, research was conducted on digital journals indexed by Scopus, Emerald, Jstor, Ebsco Hot and digital books, which allowed the construction of the theoretical references in the study, critical thinking, rigor and systematicity are taken as part of the method to achieve a valid and accepted scientific state.

The population consisted of all the family businesses in the Asentamiento Humano 16 de octubre of the city of Chachapoya-Peru, which, according to information obtained,

were 26 businesses involved. The sample covered family businesses in the commercial sector, excluding other sectors, due to the specifications and responsibilities, in correspondence the research of Cui et al. (2017) and Pindado et al. (2012). These companies belong to the settlement 16 de octubre of the city of Chachapoyas in Peru, The final sample consists of 26 companies, covering data from the period 2021 to 2022 with a confidence level of 95%. To select the sample, the Simple Random technique was used, using the corresponding statistical formula. To select the sample, the non-probabilistic intentional technique was used.

The present research work involves the collection and systematic graphical representation of data to provide a clear idea of a given situation. The technique used was the survey, a 19-item questionnaire was applied for the present research work; The research instrument was validated with the alpha method and Cronbach and Pearson which allowed me to point out that the tool used to assess the instrument used is highly significant and reliable, this instrument was applied to all family businesses.

Figure 2. Procedure

For the analysis and data processing of the information obtained in this research, the latest version of SPSS was used, which allowed the quantification of the information.

Reliability statistics

Cronbach's alpha	N of elements
0.841	26

4. Results

The city of Chachapoyas was founded by the Spanish in Peru, it is a colonial area in the department of Amazonas, its geographical location is in the northeastern part, it assumes significant roles as a political, administrative, financial, tourist, and specifically commercial center, becoming a multifunctional city, whose essential function is to provide goods and services to consumers who live in a certain space that goes beyond its limitations. Its spatial scope covers an occupied urban area of 369.22 hectares (PDU of Chachapoyas, 2013). According to the 2017 census it has 32,026 inhabitants and its annual growth rate during the period 1993 to 2007, was 2.81%, and between 2007 to 2017 it increased to 3.3% annually.

Table 1. Characteristics of family businesses

Companies	f	%
Family-owned	20	76.92
Artisanal	6	23.08
Individuals	0	0.00
Family-owned company	0	0.00
Total	26	100.00

Table 1 shows that according to the characterization of family businesses in the commerce sector, the most commonly identified in the human settlement 16 de Octubre, Chachapoyas, Amazonas, are family-owned businesses with 76.92% and artisanal businesses with 23.08%.

On the elements of raising awareness of the business formalization of family businesses in the commerce sector in the human settlement 16 de octubre, Chachapoyas, Amazonas, Peru, in the year 2021 , different behaviors are shown.

Table 2. Level of Organizational Behavior

Level	f	%
Good	1	3.8
Regular	1	3.8
Mala	24	92.3
Total	26	100

Table 2 shows the level of behavior related to the level of awareness received with regard to the formalization of family businesses in the commerce sector in the human settlement 16 de octubre, Chachapoyas, Amazonas, where 92.3% indicate that they have not received any awareness talks, which is rated as bad, but it can be seen from the research that there are owners of this establishment who have been able to read some of the regulations given by the National Customs and Excise Superintendency.3% indicate that they have not received any awareness-raising talks, but the research shows that there are owners of this establishment who have been able to read some of the regulations issued by the National Superintendency of Customs and Tax Administration (SUNAT), leaving aside the regulations established by the Municipality of Chachapoyas-Peru, which is reflected in a good and regular incidence of 3.8%.

In the number of family businesses formalized in the commerce sector in the Asentamiento Humano 16 De Octubre, Chachapoyas, Amazonas, Peru, in the year 2021 - 2022.

Table 3. Formalization of the commercial organization

Level	f	%
Good	4	15.4
Regular	7	26.9
Mala	15	57.7
Total	26	100

Table 3 clearly shows that 57.7% still cannot be formalized and therefore consider that the work done is bad and only 15.4% is good and that they wish to formalize.

On the percentage of family businesses in the commerce sector that access business formalization in the human settlement 16 de Octubre, Chachapoyas, Amazonas, Peru, 2021-2022.

Table 4. Behavior of Family Businesses

Level	f	%
Good	0	0.0
Regular	4	15.4
Mala	22	84.6
<u>Total</u>	<u>26</u>	<u>100</u>

Table 4, in accordance with the proposed general objective, shows that, according to the expected results, only 15.4% of the companies have been formalized and that the vast majority (84.6%) do not wish to formalize.

5. Discussion

In the identification of family businesses in the commerce sector in the human settlement 16 de octubre, Chachapoyas, Amazonas, Peru, in the year 2022. According to Comex Peru, published in the magazine *Economía & Negocio* (2022), the in situ assessment shows that 65.3% of the companies are informal, and most of these companies are family businesses, therefore, the jobs are not paid and there is no way to guarantee health insurance or pensions for the workers.

The sector with the lowest number of informal family businesses is located in the southern part of the country. In the provinces of Tacna, Moquegua, Arequipa, Apurímac and Madre de Dios, the informality rate of family businesses ranges between 80% and 85%. These areas also include Lima (Central Coast), Junín (Central Highlands) and La Libertad (North Coast). "The increase in informality makes it necessary to take immediate action, more so if one considers that currently 96% of companies in Peru and 75.3% of exporting companies are Mypes, policies that make family businesses have to go uphill will only have repercussions in more informality and disruption of the structure of export operations." According to the results obtained during the present investigation, it was determined that, according to Table 1, the family businesses in the commerce sector that are most identified in the human settlement 16 de octubre, Chachapoyas, Amazonas, are family businesses with family capital with 76.92% and artisanal businesses with 23.08%, which confirms that most of the family businesses in the settlement are informal.

.In relation to raising awareness in the business formalization of the commerce sector in the Asentamiento Humano 16 de octubre, Chachapoyas, Amazonas, Peru, in the year 2022. According to the analysis criteria, we have that according to Diaz (2017), 10% of entrepreneurs in the Pimentel region receive continuous training to grow their business, and a total of 54% of entrepreneurs sometimes and rarely receive training to grow their business and achieve the normalization of their business. The most striking figure is that 36% of businesses have never received such benefits, but Chambi (2016) concludes that they represent a high proportion of the total number of businesses throughout Peru, with family businesses covering a large part of the economic activity.

When a business is started, over the years it becomes a large enterprise. Table 2 shows the level of behavior related to the level of awareness received with respect to the formalization of business in the commerce sector in the human settlement of 16 de octubre, Chachapoyas, Amazonas, where 92.3% indicate that they have not received any awareness talk, but the research shows that there are owners of this establishment who have been able to read some regulations issued by SUNAT but not by the Municipality of Chachapoyas, which is reflected in a good and regular incidence of 3.8%.

Respect in the determination in formalized family businesses in the commerce sector in the human settlement 16 de octubre, Chachapoyas, Amazonas, Peru, in the year 2022. According to Diaz (2017), 40% of the total population of entrepreneurs in the district of Pimentel are not registered in the municipality, while 60% are officially registered in the district municipality, which contributes to the existence of informality in the district. The assumption that the formalization of street trade in the city of Chepén is the lack of culture and the high costs of formalizing its development in the area, for data collection was used surveys of traders and interviews with officials without any scale to draw conclusions Yes, 33.33% of street vendors in the boulevard Ezequiel González Cáseda of the city of Chepén is considered formalizing their business. Taking into account the results obtained in Table 3, it is clear that there are still businesses that need to be formalized and above all that a

common effort should be made between the institutions and the university so that in one way or another the businesses can be formalized because 57.7% are still reluctant to formalize.

Likewise, in determining the percentage of family businesses in the commerce sector that have access to business formalization in the Asentamiento Humano 16 de octubre, Chachapoyas, Amazonas, Peru, 2022. In the evaluation criteria, we can highlight the point of view given according to Diaz (2017), of the total population of microentrepreneurs in the district of Pimentel, 75% of the respondents did not know anything about the law, and likewise, 25% of the respondents knew the laws of family businesses, the vast majority of entrepreneurs do not understand what tax culture is or means, and this is because in the Province of Kutwo, the entities in charge of tax administration do not understand the tax culture to have business in those provinces. They themselves stated that they did not know how to formalize their businesses and where to go in this regard, which in turn further increased the rate of informalization in the mentioned provinces. According to the expected results, it can be determined in Table 4, that businessmen still do not want to formalize and that they should go deeper with training and above all explain in more detail the benefits that can be found if the companies start to formalize.

6. Conclusions

Family development largely defines the behavior and the various alliances that are made for their consolidation, with the desire to continue with the business legacy in the future and their commitment to the business are characteristics that favor formalization. It should be noted that most informal enterprises are located in the range of micro-entrepreneurs, because they are generally family businesses and their production is under the daily dynamics and the profits or profit margins are used to subsist.

In this regard, despite having sensitized businessmen, they are still reluctant to comply with their tax obligations, so it is necessary to continue with personalized training.

The formalization processes of family businesses in the commerce sector should seek new ways to pay taxes and be more accessible to tax payments. That, according to the proposed objectives and the proposed hypothesis has not been able to reach the expected result and that public institutions encourage greater outreach to them and not only through SUNAT the participation of universities plays an important role in the processes of mentoring or tutoring from the processes of linkage with the productive sector of the department of Amazonas.

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